

Cyclodextrins as Protective Hosts for Chemical UV Filters

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Abstract

UV filter – cyclodextrin complexes are computationally studied in water using all-atom molecular dynamics simulations. The chemical UV filters considered herein are octocrylene and avobenzone, which are widely used in commercial sunscreen products and together provide broad-spectrum skin protection (covering both UV-A and UV-B radiation). The selected host molecules are β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD). In general, cyclodextrins have been assessed for protecting UV filters against photodegradation and oxidation, as well as for their ability to restrict UV filter permeation into deep skin layers. In all molecular dynamics simulations, the starting point involves the UV filters and cyclodextrin molecules in the unbound state to determine whether noncovalent complexation is a spontaneous process. The primary goal is to investigate in detail the complexes from a nanoscopic point of view, as well as the complexation process, with a special focus on the thermodynamic description and the stability of the formed supramolecular complexes. In the framework of our analysis, several properties are calculated and, when possible, comparisons are made with published experimental data. Concerning thermodynamics, the binding free energy is estimated by applying a modified version of the Linear Interaction Energy (LIE) method. This method has low computational cost and has been successfully applied in a number of studies involving complexes formed between cyclodextrins and small organic molecules. With regard to avobenzone, which contains a β -diketone group, both keto and enol forms are studied due to their tautomeric equilibrium and distinct roles in photoprotection and photodegradation mechanisms.

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